

The Recurrent Presentation of Acute Pancreatitis Secondary to Pancreatic Divisum: A Case Report and Review of Literature on the Comparative Analysis of Medical versus Surgical Management

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ABSTRACT

Pancreatic Divisum is a congenital anomaly that can predispose individuals to present with acute pancreatitis. Management strategies vary, with options including medical therapy and surgical intervention. We herein present a case of a 74-years-old female with a history of Pancreatic Divisum who presented to the emergency department with the complaints of acute abdominal pain. The revised Atlanta Criteria to diagnose acute necrotizing pancreatitis was met. This case report highlights the importance of having a multidisciplinary management approach to promptly recognize pancreatic Divisum in the clinical presentation of recurrent acute pancreatitis.

Keywords: Pancreatic Divisum, Acute Pancreatitis, Multidisciplinary Management Approach

INTRODUCTION

Pancreas Divisum, a prevalent pancreatic anomaly, rarely leads to symptomatic disease in most patients. Pancreatitis secondary to pancreatic Divisum poses a challenging clinical scenario, demanding careful consideration of medical and surgical management options. About 4% of patients with pancreatic Divisum had a higher incidence of recurrent pancreatitis. While conservative medical management with supportive care with fluid replacement, pain control and nutritional support can be effective in some cases, surgical intervention may provide a more definitive solution, improving pancreatic drainage and reducing the risk of recurrent attacks. To bring to notice such clinical presentation, we report a case of recurrent acute pancreatitis complicating pancreatic Divisum. In the presented case, the patient was managed through medical approaches, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of their efficacy. The patient was informed that data concerning the case would be submitted for publication, and he provided an informed consent.

CASE DESCRIPTION

We herein present a case of a 74-years-old female with a history of Pancreatic Divisum, GERD, Type 2 DM, prior history of recurrent pancreatitis who presented to the emergency department with the complaints of acute upper abdominal pain. The pain was acute in onset, located in the upper abdomen, constant, aching, and started shortly after a meal. On the pain scale, she rated it as 10/10 in intensity. Associated symptoms included episodes of loose stools without blood or mucus and nausea with non-bloody or non-bilious vomiting. The patient denied any alcohol or tobacco product use. Past admissions for acute recurrent pancreatitis did not involve surgical intervention. The patient denies travel history, sick contact, fever, chills, shortness of breath, chest pain, palpitations, or any urinary symptoms. Her home medications included Metformin 500 mg twice daily and Omeprazole 20mg daily. On a physical exam, the patient is alert and oriented to time, person, place, BMI (30.8 kg/m²), vital signs were blood pressure of 149/81 mmHg, a pulse rate of 68/min, afebrile, and oxygen saturation at 100% on room air. The chest and heart examination were unremarkable. Neck examination did not reveal any lymphadenopathy or thyroid gland enlargement. Abdominal examination showed normal bowel sounds on auscultation and was positive for tenderness on light palpation in the epigastrium with no rebound tenderness or guarding. There was no cutaneous manifestation of acute pancreatitis such as Cullen's sign, Grey Turner's sign, Fox's sign. Labs were significant for calcium level of 7.9 mg/dL, lipase level of 504 U/L (Reference range 0-160 U/L), amylase level of 243 U/L, serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT) 104 U/L (reference range 0 – 35 U/L), aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels 246 U/L (reference range 15- 46 U/L) despite normal bilirubin levels, alkaline phosphatase (ALKP) 122 (reference range 38-126 U/L), Lactic acid of 2.5, total bilirubin 1.7 (reference range 0.1-1.2 mg/dL), Direct bilirubin of 0.6 (reference range <0.3 mg/dL), and hepatitis panel negative. Immunoglobulin G4 (IgG4) was within the reference range (682 mg/dL). The coagulation profile was within normal values. The remainder of his complete blood count including White blood cell counts, serum electrolytes, serum calcium, serum creatinine, and serum urea, serum cholesterol, and serum triglycerides were all within their reference range. COVID negative rapid test and Urine Drug screen were unremarkable. Serum Ethanol levels were negative. Chest Xray showed normal cardiac silhouette with no focal pulmonary consolidation or pleural effusion. Electrocardiogram (EKG) demonstrated sinus bradycardia (rate 58 beats per minute) with no ST segment, T wave changes. Abdominal Ultrasound was performed and noted GB wall thickening but no intrahepatic biliary duct dilatation. Computed tomography (CT) Abdomen and Pelvis on admission (**Figure 1**) day was subsequently performed and showed an enlarged and edematous appearance of the pancreas. The pancreatic ducts were not dilated with no biliary ductal dilation or obstructing calculi visualized in the biliary tree. The gall bladder was distended (4.5 cm) without radio-opaque stones, wall thickening or pericholecystic fluid, and reactive duodenitis. These findings are suggestive of acute interstitial edematous pancreatitis. There was no evidence of drainable fluid collections or intra-abdominal free air. The patient had no Systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) criteria. BISAP Score (entailing: BUN, Impaired mental status, SIRS, Age > 60 years, and presence of pleural effusion) calculated from the labs and data on the first 24 hours of admission was score 0 (indicating less than 1% of mortality), and CT severity index (Balthazar score) was C (indicating mild interstitial pancreatitis without pancreatic or extra pancreatic necrosis). Given the patient clinical presentation of abdominal pain, and lipase levels elevation more than three times the upper limit of normal, the revised Atlanta Criteria to diagnose mild acute interstitial edematous pancreatitis (IEP) was met. A prior MRCP (**Figure 2**) revealed a

crossing duct sign with drainage into the minor papillae indicating a pancreatic Divisum anatomy. The blood tests and imaging studies ruled out gallstones, alcohol, or hyperlipidemia as possible causes of acute pancreatitis. The patient was admitted to the Intensive Care Unit for further management. The patient was made NPO, and IV fluids (2-3 liters Lactate Ringer IV) were started in a peripheral line. Pain control was managed with morphine IV. The patient was kept on medical treatment for acute pancreatitis and her symptoms gradually resolved on the 7th day of hospital admission, her Lipase trended downward and normalized (4000 > 504). A multidisciplinary team approach was coordinated between gastroenterologist and general surgeons. Given that this presentation constituted the 5th recurrence and admission due to acute pancreatitis, the patient was offered surgical intervention, but she declined. The patient clinically improved, and all her symptoms resolved, and she was counseled on the importance of outpatient follow-up, and she was discharged home.

Figure 1: CT Abdomen without Contrast agent showing Pancreas segmentation in the Axial plane. Finding of acute interstitial pancreatitis. There is a borderline enlarged and possibly edematous appearance of the pancreas.

Figure 2: Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) showing pancreatic Divisum.

DISCUSSION

Pancreatic Divisum is a congenital anomaly that can predispose individuals to pancreatitis. Management strategies vary, with options including medical therapy and surgical intervention. Our case report adds to a handful list of

cases discussing the presentation, diagnostic evaluation, and comparative outcomes of medical and surgical management in a 74-year-old female with pancreatic Divisum, and a history of acute recurrent pancreatitis. Pancreatitis secondary to pancreatic Divisum poses a challenging clinical scenario, demanding careful consideration of medical and surgical management options. The initial medical management approach employed conservative strategies aimed at alleviating the patient's symptoms and promoting pancreatic healing. Pain control, achieved through appropriate analgesics, played a pivotal role in enhancing the patient's comfort. Adequate hydration and fasting help to reduce the workload on the pancreas, facilitating its recovery. Enzyme replacement therapy, involving the administration of pancreatic enzymes, addressed the deficiency resulting from abnormal drainage, aiding digestion and nutrient absorption. In contrast, the surgical approach, specifically endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) with sphincterotomy and stent placement, targeted the underlying anatomical abnormality. By performing sphincterotomy, the sphincter of Oddi, a muscular valve controlling the flow of pancreatic juices into the duodenum. This intervention directly addresses the pancreatic Divisum root cause, facilitating the drainage of pancreatic secretions into the duodenum, thereby reducing the risk of obstruction and subsequent pancreatitis episodes. This proactive approach aimed at preventing future episodes of pancreatitis by resolving the underlying anatomical issue. This underscores the significance of a stepwise approach, reserving surgery for specific scenarios with individualized assessment and timely intervention.

In this case report, our patient was evaluated for both medical and surgical therapy and responded to medical management. Surgical management was not considered due to risk of complications. The choice between medical and surgical management should be tailored to the individual patient's clinical presentation and response to initial therapy, considering the potential risks and benefits.

To date, there are no specific guidelines for the management of recurrent pancreatitis secondary to Pancreatic Divisum. Further research and long-term follow-up studies are essential to guide the optimal management strategy for patients with Pancreatic Divisum, considering the complexity of the condition and its impact on the patient's quality of life. A multidisciplinary team approach including early consultation with surgeons in managing Pancreatic Divisum is warranted for sound management plan.

CONCLUSION

Pancreas Divisum, a prevalent pancreatic anomaly, rarely leads to symptomatic disease in most patients. However, when complications arise, necessitating intervention, endoscopic drainage is the initial approach. Surgical treatment becomes imperative following endoscopic drainage failure or when complications like chronic pancreatitis and local complications emerge. This underscores the significance of a stepwise approach, reserving surgery for specific scenarios where conservative or endoscopic methods prove insufficient. Individualized assessment and timely intervention are crucial, ensuring that surgical options are judiciously applied, enhancing the overall management of pancreas Divisum-related complications. ***This case report highlights*** the importance of having a multidisciplinary management approach and having a high index of suspicion regardless of symptomatology to promptly recognize pancreatic Divisum as a cause of the clinical presentation of recurrent acute pancreatitis.

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Conflict of Interest: None

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